

REPRESENTATION OF REFERENTIAL SITUATIONS IN ENGLISH LITERARY TEXT AND ITS TEMPORAL COMPONENT AS EXPRESSION OF THE SPEAKER'S INNER-TIME CONSCIOUSNESS

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this work is to convey the information about referential situation in English language. The categories of tense, aspect, and perfect of the English verbal forms used in speech are the main focus of the study since they express the temporal aspect of the linguistic consciousness of the speaker. The examination of the phenomenological theory of intentionality introduces the idea of inner-time consciousness as the underlying idea for all signitive intentions. The linguistic signs are viewed as tools for expressing and reconstructing the mental representations of the speaker that comprise up temporal sense.

Key words: *theory of translation, equivalency of translation, the English language, inner time consciousness, language consciousness, signitive intention, referential situation, predication, temporality, English verb tense system.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель данной работы – передать информацию о референтной ситуации на английском языке. Категории времени, вида и перфекта английских глагольных форм, используемых в речи, являются основным предметом исследования, поскольку выражают временной аспект языкового сознания говорящего. Исследование феноменологической теории интенциональности вводит идею внутреннего времени сознания как основную идею всех означающих намерений. Языковые знаки рассматриваются как инструменты выражения и реконструкции мысленных представлений говорящего, составляющих временной смысл.

One of the most sophisticated forms of intellectual effort for humans is translation, which is one of the forms of interlingual and intercultural communication. This kind of activity involves every aspect of the speaker's consciousness. With sign intention is a subject-translator. Any person who speaks has the objective of conveying a sign in the form of a message through her words. The translator sets himself this objective by operating in accordance with the meanings provided by a speaker of a different language. It is obvious that an exhaustive analysis of the issues involved in converting communications across different natural languages can only be done from the perspective of an interdisciplinary linear approach. But philologists and linguists were

the first to tackle the issues with contemporary translation studies. The study of translation is not a linguistic phenomenon; rather, it is a subfield of linguistics. However, referring to some language knowledge notions can be helpful, particularly the idea of linguistic consciousness of speech communication subjects, which explains how different linguistic worldviews materialize. There is undoubtedly room to examine some significant translation-related difficulties. One of these is the idea of an objective situation (SS), which is frequently employed in translation studies to assess the level of translation equivalence and to correlate the communicative, substantive, and formal plans of the original and later updated texts. We branch out outside of the field of linguistics itself and explore a notion from the philosophy of consciousness. The need for such a solution is already ingrained in the idea of linguistic consciousness that is conveyed in the linguistic representation of the world by native speakers of the language. Due to the peculiarities of the translation industry, the intersubjective meaning-making consciousness structures of the translator as a speaking subject are the main workers. According to a limited interpretation, only denotative language functions as opposed to expressive, volitional, metalinguistic, factual, and aesthetic functions are responsible for the manifestation of PS. According to our understanding, the extra-linguistic situation contains more than just the pre-elements and the relationships between them that make up the message's content. It also contains the subject's attitude, which is based on the speaker's strong ties to his environment and influences the choice of extralinguistic content and linguistic resources. You can make substantial progress in understanding the speaker's motivations, objectives, and pragmatic attitude if you correctly "read" the speaker's stance. The identified equivalences can take up various positions in the FL and TL systems because each language has its own system of forms and meanings. According to J. Catford, translation equivalence does not imply the semantic or for-little equivalency of texts in FL and TL. His fundamental concern is that texts must be equivalent from a substantive and communicative point of view and be able to substitute one another in a given circumstance. This problem is made clearer by the idea of an objective circumstance that we are thinking about both formally and substantively. Additionally, the situation can be used as a subject for comparative analysis to determine how much the language units used in FL and TL are equivalent to one another and to pinpoint the formal and substantive differences between two texts that are communicatively equivalent in FL and TL. Therefore, from the perspective of translation, the subject situations of two equivalent texts might, and in some cases, should, differ from one another. These are PS1 (the original, primary text) and PS2 (the translated, secondary text), which differ from one another due to, among other things, the linguistic awareness of native

speakers of the two languages. The link between lexical semantics and ideas, as well as differences in their grammatical systems, make it evident that absolute equivalence between translations of the desired pair of languages cannot be attained. In general, we suspect that contemporary technologies will aid in the resolution of the translation equivalency issue. scientific research on speech behavior. Predicative intent forms the foundation of any objective circumstance. To put it another way, consciousness and language are the foundations of consciousness. The topic of the speech, which is presented in a specific fashion, is set up in the center beneath the speaker's manic expression. Since the assignment of occurrences to time, characteristics assigned to the topic of speech must obviously have a temporal aspect. This axis represents the normal course of events. In fact, the speaker expresses his awareness of his presence in space and time as well as the facts related to it. Therefore, one of the most crucial elements of the subject situation is the predicative part, which is highly calling, primarily represented in a range of linguistic forms, and either developed to its fullest form or compressed into personal degree. Three different time ideas will be noted: 1) Physical time, as determined by natural and scientific means, is contrasted with the human subject as being neutral, objective, and independent of his existence; Time is a linguistic category and a component of the natural sign language. It is also phenomenological, internal, and one of the meaningful experiences a person might have. In essence, all three ideas are the same. Physical time is represented in internal experience by phenomenological time. Cancel We should point out that what we refer to as "experience" here is a phenomenon rather than a psychological concept, it is "understanding" that purposeful consciousness creates about the object of sensory experience as it attempts to make sense of its surroundings. Any meaning can be connected to meaning and reaches the category level. kovaya consciousness's intended state. Internal time unites all semantic experiences penetration into the holistic objective world of consciousness, phenomena of consciousness. Internal time manifests itself in the mechanisms of consciousness of internal time, allowing realize each experience as a long one, having different temporary phases PS, and the final thing. In everyin the meaning-making act, the "now/now" phases are experienced, "before", "after" and their various modes, for example, "just now", "recently", "previously" and many others. The connection of various moments is ensured by the mechanism mothers of retention (retention by consciousness of experienced meanings) and protention (pro- predicting subsequent meanings). Objects of consciousness are thought of as simultaneous variable, either as following one after another, or as preceding one to another. In other words, any formation of meaning in consciousness is interconnected associated with other semantic experiences in a temporal sequence,

forming an endless horizon in the mind. Founder of classical phenomenology Edmund Husserl wrote: "...We will take all phenomenological sk temporary field of the pure Self, which this Self can, based on any of its experiences, measured in three dimensions - what is "before", what is "after" le", to that what is "simultaneously"; ...we will take the whole, united in its essence- ity and a strictly self-contained flow of temporary unities of experience" [3]. Consciousness of inner time is the foundation on which everything rests sense-giving consciousness, its organizing center. The speaker has the chance to use lexical-semantic, syntactic, and other linguistic tools to convey the event's temporal placement. The latter are the primary objective methods of communicating interim plans, thus we are interested in them for this piece. We don't take into account how to communicate subjective modality. In regard to the subjective consciousness of time, the grammatical category of tense in modern English is sufficient yet obvious. It has the ability to represent the full range of temporal meanings in their intricate relationships, according to how the subject of the speech understands and expresses them, without the necessity for lexical devices, though those are nonetheless employed occasionally. For instance, there are at least two methods to express a meaningful experience of a past event. In particular, the Present Perfect predicate indicates the links between two transitory plans, namely the present instant of speech and some past moment, to which the stated fact pertains, in a clear and understandable manner. The speaker's attention is focused on the "Now" of the time of utterance, but it is expressed using a language category that denotes an activity that physically links to the past. When two temporal layers are united in a single instant of perceiving meaning during awareness burning, something that is physically impossible occurs. In fact, the meaning of the pro-shalom action is retained in awareness (retention) and transferred to the current time of speaking. Speaker's Consciousness actualizes an action from the past, relating it to the present from the point of view of its consequences. It is no coincidence that statements with predicates in the Present Perfect are easy interpreted using verbs in the present tense. For example: 'The preconceived notion of journalism as the democratic craft to society has been redefined in today's media industry, instead, with a fixation on its role as the political craft'.

Temporal location is represented twice at several language levels, once using an adverb in the possessive form in the attributive no function and once using a complete predicate in the form of the Present Perfect Passive. The semantics of the adverb and the syntactic form of the predicate overlap at one point - the semantic experience of "now", in which, by the will of the spoken which combines modernity and the outcomes of rethinking the role of journalism in society (a process that took some time, the beginning of which is not indicated - zany speaking), which led to a new definition

of the concept of journalism. A statement with a predicate in the past tense, on the other hand, shows that the speaker is thinking about the time period "before," rather than relating the event to the present instant. The fact is perceived as being in the past and being distinct from the present. of the city and the border region next to it, extending into the past, for which which is "answered" by the Present Perfect. This is a part of a comprehensive, all-encompassing circumstance that was not mentioned by the speaker in any of his or her semantic plans when the speech was being made. For example, in the same article about the position of a journalist in society temporary society, the author continues: 'Long before journalism evolved into an episode of entertainment tonight, it held value and meaning to society. The defining role of the media as the 'watchdog' for society was held in high respect. The journalist, as a public servant, held an authority that allowed the public to have a bird's-eye view on daily events.' The verb tenses used in the predicates and semantics of the situation we identified indicate that the author is considering a portion of the time horizon "before" in this passage, which repeatedly emphasizes the significant distance between the two time periods that are the subject of the speaker's attention. An English speaker can arrange the variety of facts in a text passage with a complex structure in a unique fashion, communicating everything from the shadows of their intricate interconnections in time. The purpose of the English tense system is to allow for the temporal linkage of specific facts in bigger parts of text as well as in sayings, which may include a number of expanded and collapsed predicates. In these transient forms, the speaker communicates a portion of the meanings that are present in his temporal horizon and consciousness in the manner in which he perceives and intends to communicate them. In part, the so-called rule for agreeing tenses in complex English pronunciation sayings permits not only to formally connect polypredicate statements calling within the framework of a specific logic fixed in the language system, but also to convey or, conversely, reveal a specific part of the inner consciousness speaker's time. We can describe details of the course of action using the English verb's grammatical categories. Such possibilities of the English verb are reduced renamed in the distant past. Historical studies of Germanic languages show that Germanic The tense system is based on Indo-European forms of the species. Determined that species is a category older than time. Obviously, Germanic forms are temporary they were rethought on the basis of forms of the form, and in the past tense Germanic The verb forms combined perfect (perfect form) and aorista (instant appearance). Category of aspect expressing the duration of action events, is more recent in origin, although the specific value of the duration existed already in the Old English period, without having a special forms of expression. Over time, the species-time system has changed due to the growing need to focus on a specific point

in time (a moment of speech or a specific moment in the past or future). Arose- The emergence of the Continuous as a single analytical form dates back to the early the English period, and then a whole system of forms of long-term discharge. Along with them, a new form of perfect-long-term discharge is developing: already in the 15th century. The first cases of using Perfect Continuous tenses were registered [4]. Returning to translation issues, we note that forre-creation temporal component of the PS, it is necessary to analyze the interaction categories of tense, perfect and aspect in each verb form. It is important for the translator that every English verb is a native speaker these three grammatical categories. The verb form indicates whether speaking action refers to the past, present, future, as well as the future with accuracy ki view of the past; whether the action relates to a particular moment within given time periods or precedes this moment; and whether the action is being considered to be long-term or targeted, or has reached its limit. The speaker determines the temporal placement of predicates in complicated polypredicate utterances or in a longer section of text in accordance with the meanings of a particular segment of consciousness of internal time. Generally speaking, at the level of linguistic consciousness, the English verb's tense system permits not only the transmission of complicated modes of internal time consciousness, indicating various types of temporal interweaving of events, but also the transmission of elements of the course of action. The English verb's grammatical categories of tense, aspect, and perfect, as well as its lexical expressions of temporal semantics, all contribute to the articulation of a temporal fragment of the speaker's consciousness. It is the translator's responsibility to make it explicit in PS1's predicates and associated lexical-semantic units, and to recreate it using translation language as a component of PS2.

The list of used literature

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